

PERSONALITY MATURATION AND ACTIVITY, ITS ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY

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Abstract. *personality maturation is characterized by the fact that it has a physical, mental, Political, Legal, Moral, environmental and aesthetic aspect. These aspects of maturation are uneven, that is, they occur at different rates. For example, the physical perfection of a person is what it was 50 thousand years ago, now it is also going on almost like that. However, due to the development of thinking in the mental maturation of a person, very large positive shifts were observed. The main task of the individual is the creative assimilation of social experience formed in society and the inclusion of oneself in the system of social relations. All aspects (aspects) of the personality are manifested only in activity and communication. Activity and communication constitute two characteristics of social life, namely two ways of human life. In this article, opinions and reflections on the maturation and functioning of the individual, their role in the development of society are discussed.*

Keywords: *personality, maturity, activity, Society, Development, Communication, thinking, intelligence, social experience.*

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ И АКТИВНОСТЬ ЛИЧНОСТИ, ЕЕ РОЛЬ В РАЗВИТИИ ОБЩЕСТВА

Аннотация. *взросление личности характеризуется тем, что оно имеет физический, психический, политический, правовой, нравственный, экологический и эстетический аспекты. Эти аспекты созревания неравномерны, то есть происходят с разной скоростью. Например, физическое совершенство человека то, что было 50 тысяч лет назад, сейчас тоже происходит почти так. Однако благодаря развитию мышления в психическом созревании человека наблюдались очень большие положительные сдвиги. Главной задачей личности является творческое освоение социального опыта, сформировавшегося в обществе, и включение себя в систему общественных отношений. Все стороны (стороны) личности проявляются только в деятельности и общении. Деятельность и общение составляют две характеристики общественной жизни, а именно два образа жизни человека. В данной статье обсуждаются мнения и размышления о взрослении и функционировании личности, их роли в развитии общества.*

Ключевые слова: *личность, зрелость, активность, общество, развитие, общение, мышление, интеллект, социальный опыт.*

INTRODUCTION

Activity can be active and slow. Activity-in the process of knowledge, allows the oculist to quickly and successfully assimilate social experience, develops his abilities associated with the exchange of thoughts, forms his attitude to the surrounding being. Cognitive activity ensures the mental maturation of the child. Labor activity stimulates the rapid and successful formation of the spiritual and moral world of the individual, determines the successful preparation for Labor.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

All manifestations of activity are based only on excitations. The diversity of human extrirases gives rise to a wide variety of types of activity. Characteristic features of personality maturation: a) irreversibility; b) inextricable dependence of development and crises; C) non-observance of one rhythm; g) curve-vaporization; d) passage of phased levels; e) aspiration (inclination) for stability. Concepts of personality maturation:

1. biologized direction;
2. socialized direction;
3. bio-social orientation;
4. conceptual provisions of modern pedagogy and psychology.

Activity and communication - factors of personality maturation: A) activity and communication. their leading types; b) requirements for activity and communication; C) age characteristics of personality maturation. The relationship of enlightenment and maturation: developing educational technologies. Communities (society), which include each individual and group of individuals, are formed, operate in a certain space and time, and, ultimately, give way to younger generations. Hence, the renewal (exchange) of generations, that is, the social reproduction of generations, is a continuous process, the succession of which continues without interruption. In the conditions established in Aloxi, that is, in educational institutions, the maturation of a person's personality is one of the most complex and decisive problems of pedagogical theory and practice. This problem has different aspects and is studied by a number of natural and Social Sciences.

RESULTS

The formation and maturation of the personality is characterized by quantitative and qualitative changes, a process of consistent re-changes that lead to an increase in the level of personality maturation. Several theories have emerged about personality maturation:

1. preformist theory-a doctrine about the development of an embryo in sexual (egg, seed) cells and the presence of material structures that predetermined the characteristics of the organism that arise from it; the theory that a person's personality is formed on the basis of a pre-given or prescribed "program" and that the qualities, characteristics of a person develop on their own,
2. theological theory-the internal program of personality maturation is the connection of a person with the divine function, duty, that is, the maturation of a person is determined by Allah. Man is a combination of two Genesis, that is, physical and spiritual sources (factors). Spiritual Genesis - "immortal soul" puts a person above nature, serves as a guarantee of communication with God. The meaning of the human mind consists in a deep understanding of the "extremely emotional world", which is revealed through faith-faith.
3. existentialist (extreme individualism) theory - society negatively affects the individual, and a person achieves perfection only when he is separated from him, that is, he himself and nature determine the maturation of the individual in advance. In other words, nothing and no one needs a person to mature.
4. biological theory-the development of an individual from the fetus repeats all the other stages that a person goes through in the process of his development as a species, that is, according to the laws of heredity (nature) on the basis of actions (behavior) associated with innate feelings, inclinations and exhilarations that a person has. Matures as a person.

5. the theory of self - maturation-a person depends only on hereditary factors (eye color, blood group, Rhesus factor, schizophrenia, etc.).k.) with support, develops under their influence, matures;
6. psychoanalytic theory - the higher the level of sexual desire (desire, aspiration) under the influence of mental strength, the faster a person develops, matures.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of citing these theories is to identify the relevant theories on which the science of pedagogy relies when studying the problems of personality maturation. Therefore, in pedagogical and psychological scientific studies on the problem of personality, the biological, socialized and bio-social directions of personality maturation are distinguished:

1. Representatives of the biologized direction believe that a person is a separate natural being, explaining the hulk character of a person by natural exhilarations, inclinations and feelings that are given to him from birth (3. Freud et al.). Representatives of this direction believe that a person is forced to obey the requirements of society, but in this, the natural exhilarations of the individual are somehow artificially suppressed by society. That is, the non-satisfaction of natural exhilarations is replaced by training in some kind of activity, and to what extent the constant internal struggle of a person with himself is masked and closed.
2. Representatives of the socialized direction argue that if a person is born as a biological being, Ham will gradually socialize under the influence of social groups with which he communicates in the process of his life. The lower the level of maturation of the individual, the more vivid, powerful the biological characteristics are manifested in him, first of all, such innate feelings (involuntary movements) as possession, destruction, sexual inclinations. Representatives of this direction believe that a child - like a "clean cocoon"; his maturation will fully depend on the conditions and enlightenment in the environment.
3. Representatives of the bio-social orientation believe that the psychic processes that take place in a person (intuition, perception, thinking are of a biological nature, but the aspiration, interest, ability of a person is formed as a social phenomenon.

The main task of the individual is the creative assimilation of social experience formed in society and the inclusion of oneself in the system of social relations. All aspects (aspects) of the personality are manifested only in activity and communication. Activity and communication constitute two characteristics of social life, namely two ways of human life. Activity is a way of life and a form of existence of a person, the activity of which is aimed at a purposeful re-transformation of the surrounding world. The main types of activities are gaming, reading and cocktail activities. There are different classifications of types of activities: in sociology - labor, socio-political, artistic-creative, scientific-research activities; in pedagogy - labor. Reading and gaming activities; in psychology - the types of activities associated with mental processes are distinguished. Activity is a person's way of being and Living (Living. livelihood) as a form:

1. it ensures the creation of material conditions of human life, the satisfaction of natural human needs;
2. becomes a factor in the development of the spiritual world of a person, a form and condition for the satisfaction of his cultural needs;
3. The sphere of realization of a person's own personal capabilities, life goals and success is considered;

4. in the system of social relations of a person, he creates conditions for his identity to be bypassed by namo and realize his social aspirations;
5. scientific knowledge is the source and criterion of self-knowledge and self-maturation;
6. provides knowledge and re-transformation of the surrounding world.

Activity can be active and slow. Activity, in the process of which allows the student to quickly and successfully master social experience, develops his abilities associated with the exchange of thoughts, forms his attitude to the surrounding being. Cognitive activity ensures the mental maturation of the child. Labor activity stimulates the rapid and successful formation of the spiritual and moral world of the individual, determines the successful preparation for Labor. All manifestations of activity are based only on excitations. The diversity of human extrirases gives rise to a wide variety of types of activity.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, personality maturation is a complex, long - lasting conflict process characterized by a dialectical transition from quantitative changes to qualitative changes in the physical, mental and spiritual properties of a person. Personality maturation is a general category of psychological and Pedagogical Sciences, while Psychology interprets the laws of personality maturation, pedagogy creates a theory about the management of personality maturation, pursuing the goals of forming a perfect person and a harmonious generation.

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